

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

While the summer is not quite over yet in Europe (we hope), I am going to sneak out for a few days of holidays in Spain. Hence, while you read the three interesting papers in this issue I will indulge in some other pleasures for a change!

I will have important news for you in the next or next but one issue: the negotiations with Springer about how J.UCS will continue from 2000 onwards are reaching its final stage: I think chances are good that J.UCS will get quite a boost!

Yours cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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